

HEALTHCARE-ASSOCIATED INFECTIONS IN GENERAL SURGERY – PREVENTION, CONTROL AND SHARED RESPONSIBILITY

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Abstract

Nosocomial infections (Healthcare-Associated Infections) represent one of the most important challenges of modern surgery, having a major impact on morbidity, mortality and hospital costs. In general surgery, the risk is amplified by the invasive nature of the interventions and the vulnerability of patients in the postoperative period. This article analyzes the main types of surgical-associated infections, specific risk factors, current prevention and control strategies, as well as the importance of the shared responsibility of the entire medical team in reducing these adverse events.

Keywords: nosocomial infections, general surgery, prevention, control, medical responsibility

Introduction

Healthcare-associated infections, traditionally called nosocomial infections, remain a major public health problem, affecting up to 5–10% of hospitalized patients, according to WHO data. In general surgery, these infections frequently manifest as wound infections, post-catheterization urinary tract infections, ventilator-associated pneumonia, and systemic infections (sepsis, bacteremia).

Reducing the incidence of these complications requires an integrated approach, based on standardized protocols, continuous vigilance, and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Etiopathogenesis

The most common infections encountered in surgical practice are:

- Surgical wound infections – represent 30–50% of nosocomial infections in surgery. They can be superficial (skin, subcutaneous tissue) or deep (fascia, peritoneal cavity). Predominant germs: *Staphylococcus aureus* (including MRSA), *Enterococcus* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.
- Postoperative respiratory infections – often associated with intubation and mechanical ventilation, especially after major abdominal interventions.
- Urinary tract infections – frequently secondary to prolonged urinary catheterization, especially in elderly patients or with comorbidities.
- Systemic infections (sepsis) – may arise from postoperative bacterial dissemination, contaminated drainage or inadequately treated wound infections.

Predisposing factors can be grouped into three categories:

- Patient-related factors: advanced age, diabetes mellitus, obesity, malnutrition, immunosuppression, prolonged hospitalization;
- Intervention-related factors: long operative time (>2 hours), blood loss, use of implants or prostheses, intraoperative contamination;
- Environmental and personnel-related factors: failure to comply with asepsis rules, incorrect hand washing, incorrect use of antibiotics, overloading of wards.

Prevention and control

1. Preoperative measures

- Assessment and optimization of the patient's general condition (glycemic control, correction of anemia, preoperative hygiene);
- Appropriate antibiotic prophylaxis: administered 30–60 minutes before incision, according to current guidelines (e.g. cefazolin 1–2 g i.v.);
- Rigorous preparation of the surgical field (atraumatic hair removal, correct antisepsis).

2. Intraoperative measures

- Strict adherence to the rules of asepsis and antisepsis;
- Limiting the duration of the intervention and excessive tissue manipulation;
- Effective control of hemorrhage and use of sterile materials;
- Adequate ventilation in the operating room and periodic microbiological control of air and surfaces.

3. Postoperative measures

- Careful monitoring of wounds and drainages;
- Correct change of dressings;
- Limiting the duration of urinary catheterization and mechanical ventilation;
- Daily reassessment of the need for empirical antibiotic therapy;
- Patient education regarding personal hygiene and early signs of infection.

The role of the medical team and shared responsibility

Prevention of nosocomial infections does not depend only on the surgeon, but on the entire team involved in patient care: doctors, nurses, auxiliary staff, epidemiologists and microbiologists. Effective communication and compliance with institutional protocols are essential.

Shared responsibility includes:

- compliance with hand hygiene (the simplest and most effective measure);
- prompt reporting of any suspected infection;
- participation in periodic training on infection control;

- involvement of hospital management in logistical support (sterile materials, equipment, internal audit).

Overall, the rate of nosocomial infections in surgical wards is 8-20%, and in ICU wards, the maximum incidence reaches 28-30%.

In the 1st Clinical Surgery Unit of Brăila County Emergency Hospital, in the last 5 years, for an average of 1750 patients discharged annually, 14.6 infections associated with the medical act were found, according to the Single Register for the Declaration of HAIs (0.85%).

According to WHO and ECDC principles, the culture of patient safety must be integrated into the daily routine, not treated as an administrative obligation.

Conclusions

1. Nosocomial infections represent a major public health problem and an important cause of postoperative morbidity in general surgery.

2. Effective prevention requires rigorous application of standard aseptic measures, judicious antibiotic prophylaxis, and continuous epidemiological surveillance.

3. Control of these infections is a shared responsibility, involving the entire medical team, from the surgeon to the auxiliary staff.

4. Continuing education and periodic auditing are essential tools for maintaining quality and safety standards in surgical practice.

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